

Nosocomial Infections (Antiseptic, Disinfectant Assay)

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Abstract:

Nosocomial infections occur within 48 hrs of hospital admission, three days of discharge, and thirty days of an operation. They affect one in ten patients admitted to hospital. Annually, this results in 5000 deaths with a cost to the National Health Service of a Billion pounds. On average, a Patient with a hospital-acquired infection spent 2.5 times longer in hospital, incurring an additional cause of 3000 pounds more than an uninfected patient. Intensive Care Units have the highest prevalence of hospital-acquired infections in the hospital setting.

The European Prevalence of infection in an intensive care study, involving over 4500 patients, demonstrated that the Nosocomial infection prevalence rate in ICU was 20.6%. ICU patients are particularly at risk from Nosocomial infections as a result of mechanical ventilation.

Result:

The organisms were grown on specific media and biochemical tests were done for future characterization. The following organisms were identified,

1. Staphylococcus spp
- 2 .Escherichia spp
3. Salmonella spp
4. Pseudomonas spp
- 5.Klebsiella spp.

Key Words: Pathogen, Nosocomial Infections, Antiseptics.

Introduction

Nosocomial Infections:

Hospital infection is defined as any infection acquired in the hospital, where many sick people together stay under one roof. The hospital infection does not show any evidence of being present

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or incubating at the time of admission but was acquired as a result of a hospital stay. The word “Nosocomial” is derived from the Greek word for hospital. The term also includes infections acquired in nursing homes and other healthcare facilities.

Nosocomial infections result from the interactions of several factors:

1. Sources of Microorganisms that can cause infection.
2. Routes of transmission of the Microorganism.
3. Host susceptible to infection by the Microorganism.

Microbes that cause nosocomial infections are the major sources of hospital environment. They do not cause disease in healthy people but are pathogenic to individuals who have weakened defense systems by illness or therapy. **Staphylococcus aureus** was the primary source of Nosocomial infections, but nowadays Gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are also responsible for Nosocomial infections. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* can cause opportunistic skin infections, especially in surgical wounds and burn patients.

Sources of infection may be:

1. From patients, humans and hospital staff.
2. From environment and
3. From inanimate objects, food, water fomites etc.

The important routes of spread of infection in hospitals are:

1. Airborne
2. By contact
3. Common Vehicle.

Burns, surgical wounds, trauma, injection, invasive diagnostic procedures, ventilators, intravenous therapy and urinary catheters are the first line of defence and make a person more susceptible to disease in hospital. Burn patients are more susceptible to nosocomial infections because their skin is no longer an effective barrier to microorganisms. The risk of infection is also related to other invasive infections such as administering anesthesia, which may alter respiration and contribute to pneumonia and tracheotomy in which an incision is made into the trachea to assist breathing.

Many diagnostic and therapeutic hospital procedures provide a fomite route of transmission. The uncleaned urinary catheter used to drain urine from the urinary bladder is a fomite in many Nosocomial infections. An intravenous catheter, which passes through the skin and into a vein to provide fluids, nutrients or medicates can also transmit Nosocomial infections. Respiratory aids can introduce fluids or contaminate the lungs. Unsterilized needles may

introduce pathogens into muscle or blood and surgical dressings can become contaminated and promote disease.

The infections, that are common in Nosocomial infections, are surgical wound infections, infections in the urinary and respiratory tracts, and bacteraemia. Each may be acquired from an exogenous or endogenous source or even the self-source. In the early years, the Nosocomial infections were very severe and due to that the death rate was high, but nowadays due to prevention and control, hospital infections have decreased.

For the reasons outlined above, the prevention of hospital infections deserves a very high priority.

There are three main strategies for preventing hospital infections, namely

1. Excluding sources of infection from the hospital environment,
2. Interrupting the transmission of infection from source to susceptible host (breaking the chain of infection), and
3. Enhancing the host's ability to resist infection.

The incidence of hospital-acquired pathogen transmission and its effects on disinfectants and antiseptics are the subjects of this report.

Literature Review

Patients were discharged from the hospitals during the period and 25% of patients were considered to have developed Nosocomial infections. The highest rates were observed for surgical services, with the next highest rates on the obstetric and nursery services. Medical and pediatric services have the lowest rates of Nosocomial infections. [Theodore C. Eickhoff et al., 1969]

The local applications of certain commercially available antimicrobials are of no proven value. Noble et al.,(1980), suggested rigorous aseptic technique with strict hand washing to the best method of preventing bacterial colonization.

Sherman et al., (1980) suggested that if sepsis develops, the initial treatment should be an antibiotic effective against **Pseudomonas aeruginosa** as well as against other commonly grown negative organisms. Thus, the present investigation is to try all this void.

Lowbury et al.,(1970) showed that the potentially important sources were plastic wash bowls, floors and floor mops, sinks and sink mops, bed clothing, shelves and also the medical instruments.

The aerobic gram-negative rods causing Nosocomial bacteria have been characterized by multiple antimicrobial resistances, often mediated by transmissible plasmids. [Neolia L.Lima.,1983]

The majority of Nosocomial **Pseudomonas aeruginosa** infections were found on the surgical and medical services. The work of Sheretz et al.,(1983)revealed that the most common sites of Nosocomial **Pseudomonas aeruginosa** infection were the lower respiratory tract and urinary tract followed by the bloodstream and surgical wounds.

Martin J. Blaser et al., (1984) on the use of hot water in laundries formed the basis for hospital laundry policies. The work showed that exposure to a water temperature of greater than 71.1⁰c for 25 minutes would kill nearly all bacterial forms other than spores.

Besides harming patients, Nosocomial infections can affect nurses, physicians, aides, visitors, salespeople, delivery personnel, custodians and anyone who has contact with the hospital.[Harries et al.,(1984)]

Large urban centres pose specific epidemiological due to the size and motility of their population and the concentration, in a limited area, of a sizeable number of large healthcare facilities. Under these circumstances, the inter-hospital spread of Nosocomial infections can be of epidemiological significance. Schaefer et al., (1984)]

Elliott (1988) showed that **Klebsiella are** important organisms causing Nosocomial pneumonia, bacteremia, intravascular device infection and urinary tract infection.

Montgomerie et al., (1989) suggested the use of cotton swabs moistened with sterile normal saline without preservation for obtaining cultures and the swabs should be plated within an hour of collection on specific media.

Newborns are particularly susceptible to hospital-acquired infections and **Salmonellae** are of the major importance in this regard. [J.A. Roud et al.,(1986)]

Urinary tract infection develops in up to 25% of the patients having short-term bladder catheterization in acute care hospitals. 74 infections were caused chiefly by gram-negative rods, **Escherichia coli** predominating. [Richard Platt et al.,1986]

Pseudomonas aeruginosa continues to be an important pathogen in hospital acquired infections. Rossello et al.,(1992) showed that **Pseudomonas aeruginosa** accounted for 10% of such infections and ranked it the third most frequent isolates after **Escherichia coli** and **Staphylococcus aureus** . He also reported that an increased length of stay favours the

development of cross infection by **Pseudomonas aeruginosa**. This is probably related to the greater exposure to diagnostic and therapeutic manipulations and to the higher number of contacts, favouring the transmission of the organisms.

Thevenasam et al.,(1993) reported that the widespread and uncontrolled use of antibiotics and conditions such as over-crowding and poor sanitation, facilitate the spread of resistant microorganisms. Policies for the prevention of spread of resistant pathogens in hospitals in developing countries have not been properly constituted.

According to Sarma et al.,(1993) with the increase in the antibiotic usage as well as that of disinfectant usage, the incidence of totally resistant strains also showed an upward trend.

In hospital-acquired urinary tract infections, **Escherichia coli** is responsible for 50% of the infections with **Pseudomonas aeruginosa**, **Proteus SPP**, **Enterococcus**, **Staphylococcus**, Yeasts and many other organisms according to the reminder.[Anuradha De et al.,(1993)]

Approximately 40 million people are admitted to hospitals and about 2 to 4 million people may develop an infection they did not have upon entering the hospital. Thus, Nosocomial infections represent a significant proportion of all infectious diseases acquired by humans. The prolonged hospital stay leads to increased healthcare costs.[Bingen et al.,(1994)]

Antiseptics widely used in hospitals have been proven to be effective against a wide range of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, yeast and moulds but few studies have been conducted on antibiotic multi-resistant bacterial strains. [Thaore et al.,(1995)]

Resistance of Nosocomial bacteria to antimicrobials is due to both natural and acquired factors. Production of inactivating enzymes (beta-lactamases) is the most common mechanism in gram-negative bacteria. [Mainardi.II et al.,1998)]

Staphylococcus aureus has long been recognized as an important pathogen in human disease and is the most common cause of Nosocomial infections.[Perl.TM et al.,(1998)]

Hyponatremia, Anemia and the presence of a central venous catheter (CVC) are significantly associated with the risk for hospital-acquired **Staphylococcus aureus** bacteremia(SAB) report a group of Danish investigations.[Jensen AG et al.,(1999)]

Sanitary, economic and social importance of Nosocomial infections justifies the introduction and development of control and surveillance systems in hospitals.[Mariano et al.,(1999)]

Gram-negative organisms were the main pathogens isolated from patients with different forms of Nosocomial complications such as late pneumonia associated with artificial ventilation of the lungs and various secondary wound or urinary tract infections.[Karabak et al.,(2000)]

Staphylococcus aureus, Enterococci, Escherichia coli and Pseudomonas aeruginosa are most commonly identified bacteria. The most common infections were those of urinary tract infections, surgical site, blood stream infection.[Mylotte et al.,(2000)]

Method:

A hospital can be regarded as a high population density community made up of unusually susceptible people into whom the more virulent pathogens of a region are continually introduced. Because of the widespread use of the antimicrobial medications, hospital pathogens have varied susceptibility to antibiotics & disinfectants. The uncontrolled use of antibiotics & disinfectants leads to the resistance of the organism.

Thus, the present work was focused on the study of *Pseudomonas fpp*, *staphylococcus Spp*, *Escherichia Spp*, *Klebsiella spp* & *Salmonella spp* as causative agents of Nosocomial infections, studied during a period of 4 months.

The plan of work is as follows:

1. Screening the hospital environment for most frequent pathogens & determination of Pathogenic bacteria.
2. Isolation & characterization of the bacterial Pathogens.
3. To test the affects of the locally available antiseptics & disinfectants against the isolated one.

Method:

Sampling was done at Govt. hospitals. The hospital had different wards with a steady inflow of patients with various kinds of diseases.

Samples were collected from wards, OT, sterilization room, lab & from patients. In the above-mentioned areas, the chances of infection are more frequent & so these areas were selected for sampling. The samples were collected from inanimate objects such as bed linen, IV stands, sheld, tables, operation tables, food-supplying vessels, drinking water taps etc.

Sampling was done by swab technique & open plate method. In the open plate method, NA, BA, Mac. Agar was opened & kept in different areas in the hospital like corridors, wards, OT, etc for a certain period. The swabs were taken from different areas & were placed in peptone H₂O.

The tubes & plates were transported to the laboratory & then processed.

Results:

The growth of the organisms on specific media & Bcferts for further characterization of hospital isolates is as below: 1 to 4 tables.

Table 1:

S.No.	Sampling Area	Total No. of Isolates
1	Open plate method	39
2	Inanimate objects	24
3	Laboratory	5
4	Operation theater	3
5	Patients	10

Table 2:

Gram Staining

S. No.	Gram positive cocci	Gram negative rods
1	35	15

Table 3:

Biochemical Test

S.No.	Isolate	I	MR	VP	CI	Urease	TSI	Oxidase
1	E. Coli	+	+	-	-	-	A/G ⁺ H ₂ S ⁻	+
2	Klebsiella	-	-	+	+	-	A/KG ⁺ H ₂ S ⁻	+
3	Proteus	-	+	-	-	+	A/KG ⁺ H ₂ S ⁺	+
4	Salmonella	+	-	+	-	-	A/K ⁺ H ₂ S ⁺	+
5	Pseudomonas	-	-	-	-	-	-	+

Both Gram positive and Gram-negative organisms were isolated and were identified as Staphylococcus, Escherichia spp, Klebsiella spp, Proteus spp, Salmonella spp, and Pseudomonas spp.

Table 4:

Antiseptic and Disinfectant Assay

	Lizol					Phenol					Dettol				
	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E
Staphylococcus	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Escherichia	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Proteus	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
Klebsiella	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pseudomonas	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Salmonella	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-

Where A = 0.1, B = 0.2, C = 0.3, D = 0.4 and E = 0.5 respaly.

Discussion: In the recent years, the incidence due to G-ve & G+ve ough has been increasing in hospitals. In this study it was found that the total bacteria count in the various sites of the Govt. hospital was found to be relatively high. Max bacterial count was in open plate method & minimum bacterial count was found in lab & OT.

The high bacterial load in the open plate may be due to the constant movement of the Patients, Visitors, Physiotherapists, Nurses may also increase the bacterial load because they are also the carrier of the infectious pathogens.

Factors such as lower socio-economic status of the patients, patients with different type of infections, over-crowding, poor hygiene greatly contribute to the higher bacterial load.

The enumeration of hospital pathogens using specific media showed the incidence of Escherichia spp, Pneudomans spp, Klebsiella spp, Protens spp, Staphylococcus spp & Salmasella spp. Among the isolated pathogens Escherichia was predominant (33.05%), Staphylococcus spp(45.22%), Klebsiella spp(11.3%), Protens SPP(3.4%) & Salmasella spp(0.1%)

The present investigation revealed that higher incidence of all pathogens in the open plate method, Staphylococcus spp was the most common pathogen isolated from the open plate method. The reason for their existence may be due to their adaptation to grow in unfavourable conditions & their resistance to the antimicrobials used.

Conclusion:

To conclude, the total bacterial load in the Govt. hospital, was significantly high. The presence of microbial load in OT is less due to use of antiseptics on disinfectants. The present study suggests that the use of chloroxylenols as the choice of antiseptic.

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